

DRIVE FOR MONEY AND SUBSTANCE USE AS CORRELATES OF PSYCHOSOCIAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG IN-SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS IN ILISAN-REMO, IKENE LOCAL GOVT. OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Phone No: 08067985947

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16841581>

Abstract:

Every society that will be good and viable should be able to have youths or young ones that are positively minded, more focused with their academic and career, and have the ability to channel their thinking positively to make themselves and their society better, and this could only be achieved when the youths and adolescents are psychologically balanced, and have positive psychological and social behavior. Psychosocial behavior is the interplay between individual psychological and social influences, unraveling the complexities of our actions and reactions. While psychosocial behavior can be both positive (resilience, optimism, social interaction or engagement, emotional stability, assertiveness) and negative (drug abuse, cyber fraud, stealing, kidnapping, rapping, cultism). An adolescent with positive psychosocial behavior will make their environment lively, convenient and safe for living, they tends to have stronger and more supportive relationship with people and peers but when it is otherwise, the adolescents are vulnerable, they may struggle with fitting in or be prone to bullying, which can affect their thinking pattern and their social experience They may be influenced by the things around them and this will dictate to them to go for what they want rather than what they need, which makes such adolescents to be emotionally unstable, tempted to engage in lots of risky behaviors, thereby making them a bad influence to their peers and a “time bomb” to the society at large.

However, it has been observed that there are negative psychosocial behavior been exhibited by Nigerian adolescents and the issue of adolescents social decadence has become a contemporary problem in Nigeria and this has attracted the attentions of researchers and scholars from different disciplines of life (Adenike, 2013; Wang, Liu, & Ryan, 2022). Presently, adolescent’s delinquent behaviors such as drug abuse, kidnapping, raping, carrying of dangerous weapons, cyber fraud, examination malpractice, stealing and cultism seem to be on increase in Nigeria (Adenike, 2013; Ugwu. 2016). These behaviors of affluence and influence have in ways impacted some negative psychological and sociological effects on not only the adolescents but on their families and the society at large (Toyin & Aderemi, 2013). This study will focus on two major area that are likely to influence the negative psychosocial behavior of adolescents and these are drive for money and substance use.

The drive for money refers to one’s desire and aspiration for money (rather than one’s need for it or greed), including affective, behavioral, and cognitive components (Trucco, Villafuerte, Burmeister &

Zucker,2008). According to Schulenberg et al., (2022). there is an exponential increase in materialism in today's society, and the drive to get rich within a short time have contributed to the rise in financial desires among adolescents, making them to see money as a means of achieving social status, independence, and personal success. Research has further been shown that adolescents who place a high value on money and material possessions may exhibit riskier behaviors to achieve financial goals, including engaging in theft, fraudulent activities, or labor exploitation (Dittmar, Bond, Hurst & Kasser, (2014). Moreover, the pressure to contribute financially to the household, especially in low-income families, may further exacerbate this drive. Rhee et al., (2022), said financial stress at home can cause adolescents to seek various means of income, including working under harmful conditions or engaging in illegal activities. These financial motives do influence adolescents' psychosocial behavior by encouraging competition, risk-taking, and impulsivity, while also impacting their academic performance and emotional stability.

Substance abuse among adolescents is a well-documented issue that has long been linked to adverse psychosocial outcomes. According to Ames (2021). The abuse of substances such as alcohol, tobacco, marijuana, and harder drugs is often initiated due to peer influence, stress, the need for escapism, acceptability or curiosity. The accessibility of these substances has compounded the issue of psychosocial behavior. Adolescents may turn to substance use for various reasons, including peer pressure, stress relief, and the desire for social acceptance. The consequences of such behavior are profound, often leading to addiction, mental health issues, and an increased likelihood of engaging in criminal activities (Ames,2021). Substance abuse has been associated with an increased likelihood of aggression, delinquency, poor academic performance, and mental health problems such as anxiety and depression (Chaplin, . Hill & John ,2020). Consequently, substance abuse can have far-reaching effects on an adolescent's psychosocial development, as it often leads to changes in mood, cognition, and behavior. Hence,the following hypotheses are formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between drive for and psychosocial behavior of the in-school adolescents in Ilisan- Remo, Ikenne Local Government Ogun State Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between substance abuse and psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescent in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State;

H₀₃: There is no significant combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria.

Methodology:

Research Design

The study adopted a correlational research design. The choice of this particular design is based on the fact that the researchers ascertained the relationship between independent variables (Drive for money and substance use) and dependent variables (psychosocial behaviors) of in-school adolescents.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of 919 in-school adolescents, categorically from SSS 1-3 in privates and public senior secondary schools in Ilisan-remo, Ikene Local Government, Ogun State Nigeria. Six

public and private secondary schools were used, the public and private schools selected in this study are large with a moderate high population of students.

Population of Six Selected Public and private Senior Secondary Schools in Ilisan- remo and the Number of students

S/N	School	Senior Secondary School (SSS 1-3) Students' Population		
		Male	Female	Total
1	Isanbi Model high school	28	32	60
2	G.J Corner Stone High School	36	30	66
3	Ilisan High School	175	197	372
4	Isanbi comprehensive High School	98	112	210
5	Al-Lateef comprehensive high school	53	58	111
6	De-Unique international high school	47	53	100
	TOTAL	427	470	919

Source: Secretary’s office, Zonal Education Office, Ikenne Local Government Area, and Researcher’s computation, 2024.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The researcher adopted a stratified random sampling techniques for the study to ensure that every member of the population has equal and independent chance of being selected. Six public and private senior secondary schools in Ilisan-Remo were selected being an area the researcher has lived for some years. The schools were chosen based on proximity cost and availability of required data. The sample size of this study is 279 Senior Secondary school students determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula, was chosen from the population through the simple random sampling techniques. The first stage of the sampling process involves the selection of secondary schools that were used. The second stage of the sampling procedures entails the determination of the number of students that were selected from each of the schools through random sampling such that the number of students chosen from a school depends on the relative number of the students in the school. The third and final stage of the sampling process involves the actual selection of the required number of students from each of the schools through the simple random sampling technique.

The formula assumed a 95% confidence level and a 5% precision or error level. Consequently, the equation is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = sample size

N = population size, and

e = precision level (0.05)

$$n = \frac{919}{1 + 919(0.05)^2} \quad n = 279$$

Thus, the sample size of the study is 279 students.

These 279 Senior Secondary School students were proportionately distributed in Table 3.2 as the sample size for each school, using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula.

Sample of Senior Secondary Schools and the Number of Students Selected

S/N	School	Sample
1	Isanbi Model High School	18
2	Corner Stone High School	20
3	Ilisan High School	113
4	Isanbi Comprehensive High School	64
5	AL-Lateef Comprehensive high school	34
6	DE-Unique International high school	30
	TOTAL	279

Source: Researcher’s computation, 2024.

Research Instrument

The instruments used for data collection of this study is questionnaire consisting of four parts. Part A and B was designed by the researcher while part C and D was adopted.

Questionnaire - A structured and self-developed questionnaire was used and adopted by the researcher, incorporating validated scales to measure the drive for money, substance abuse, and psychosocial behavior. The questionnaire consists of four sections:

Demographic Data Inventory (DDI)

This was constructed by the researcher and was utilized to gather data on some demographic features of the participants such as Age, gender, class, and school.

Drive for Money Inventory (DFMI)

This section measures adolescent’s drive for money. It was self-developed by the researcher through study of the attributes attached to money drive, discovered through the literature. It consists of 11 items in a Likert type scale with five points responses ranging from 1= strongly disagreed to 5=strongly agreed.

Substance Abuse Inventory (SAI)

This section measures adolescent’s interest or involvement in substance use.

This is a self-report paper-and-pencil test developed by Animashahun (2007), and which assesses an individual’s propensity to substance use. It is formulated as a 5-piont Likert type scale with responses

ranging from 1= strongly disagreed to 5=strongly agreed. The test has been found to have sound psychometric indices of reliability and validity.

Psychosocial Behavior Inventory:

This section measures adolescent’s psychosocial behavior using strength and difficulties questionnaire (SDQ) developed by Robert Goodman in (1997), is a brief 25-items of behavioral and emotional difficulties that can be used to assess mental health problems in child and adolescents and 12 items were selected for the purpose of this study. It is formulated as a 5-point Likert type scale with responses ranging from 1= strongly disagreed to 5=strongly agreed. The test has been found to have sound psychometric indices of reliability and validity.

Validity of the Instrument

Validity is when an instrument measure what it’s intended to measure, (Ghauri & Gronhaug, 2005). A copy of the instrument was sent to the study supervisor and was given to an experts in test and measurement to comment and critique for improvement prior to printing and administering. Their suggestions, modifications, and comments were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument. Guaranteeing that the instrument measures the items it is intended to measure.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability is the consistency of the instrument, this is when an instrument is able to measure what it’s supposed to measure over time. The instruments was subjected to a test-retest which was conducted at two weeks’ interval. Cronbach Alpha reliability co-efficient was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. A pilot study was conducted using sample of 40 senior secondary students in Ikene local government area of Ogun state, which is outside the study area but having similar demographic characteristics. After an interval of two weeks the instruments was again administered on the same set of students. The data obtained will be subjected to Cronbach’s alpha reliability test to establish the internal consistency of the items. Results from the test were used to determine items included in the questionnaire.

Serial number	Scales	No of items	Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient
1.	Drive for money	11	.727
2.	Substance use	8	.843
3.	Psychosocial behavior	11	.863
4	Total	30	.861

Source: Researcher’s pilot study

Method of Data Collection

The students were met in their classrooms, intimated with the purpose of the study, and were informed of their freedom to decide on participating or not to participate in the exercise, then the students who decided

to participate were encouraged to give truthful and sincere responses to the questionnaire items with the assurance that information disclosed by them will be treated as confidential. Thereafter, the researcher and her assistants collected the completed questionnaires immediately and thanked the respondents and school authority for their co-operation and participation in the study. Furthermore, data analysis was performed on the collected data.

Methods of Data Analysis

The hypotheses was tested at 0.05 significance or error margin. The first and second hypotheses was analyzed using the Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficients, while the third hypothesis was tested by means of multiple regression analysis. The statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 26 programed was used to carry out all analyses.

Results:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between drive for money and psychosocial behavior of the in-school adolescents in Ilisan- Remo, Ikenne Local Government Ogun State Nigeria.

Table 1: Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficients on the relationship between drive for money and psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescent in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State

		Drive money	psychosocial behavior
Drive money	Pearson Correlation	1	.448**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	279	279
psychosocial behavior	Pearson Correlation	.448**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	279	279

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 reveals that there is a significant relationship between drive for money and psychosocial behavior of the adolescents in Ilisan- Remo, Ikenne Local Government Ogun State Nigeria.

The drive for money show a high positive relationship of 0.448* which is significant at a level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant relationship is hereby rejected and the alternate is accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between substance abuse and psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescent in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State;

Table 2: Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficients relationship between substance abuse and psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescent in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State

		Substance Abuse	psychosocial behavior
Substance Abuse	Pearson Correlation	1	.017
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.781
	N	279	279
psychosocial behavior	Pearson Correlation	.017	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.781	
	N	279	279

Table 2: reveals that there is no significant relationship between substance abuse and psychosocial behavior of the adolescents in Ilisan- Remo, Ikenne Local Government Ogun State Nigeria.

Substance abuse show a positive and insignificant relationship of 0.017 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant relationship is hereby accepted and the alternate is rejected.

H03: There is no significant combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of regression analysis for the combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria.

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	SE	Change Statistics				
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
Predictor Variables	.449 ^a	.201	.196	7.91758	.201	34.801	2		.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), substance abuse, and drive money
- b. Dependent Variable: Psychosocial behavior

The results in Table 3 indicated that with all the predictor variables (substance abuse and drive for money) in the regression model jointly influenced Psychosocial behavior ($R = .449^a$; $R^2 = .201$; $Adj. R^2 = .196$; $F(278) = 34.801$; $p = .000$). This showed that all the predictor variables accounted for 19.6% of the

variance to psychosocial behavior. The null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria was rejected by this finding. This implies that there is a significant combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria.

Table 4: Beta Coefficients for relative contributions of substance abuse, drive money on the prediction of psychosocial behavior

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-ratio	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.410	2.273		8.540	.000
	Drive money	.490	.059	.451	8.337	.000
	Substance abuse	-.043	.072	-.032	-.593	.554

a. Dependent Variable: psychosocial behavior

The results in Table 4 revealed the strength of causation of the predictor variable on the criterion variable. It was shown that all the two (2) predictors were potent enough to predict psychosocial behavior. The most potent predictor of psychosocial behavior among the predictor variables of the study is drive for money ($\beta = .451$; $t = 8.337$; $p < .05$). Substance abuse is the next potent factor ($\beta = -.032$; $t = -5.593$; $p > .05$) in the prediction of psychosocial behavior.

Discussion:

The first hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between drive for money and psychosocial behavior of the adolescents in Ilisan- Remo, Ikenne Local Government Ogun State Nigeria. This hypothesis was rejected based on a significant positive correlation which indicates that as students drive for money increases, their psychosocial behavior also tends to increase. This suggests that students who feel pressured to earn money while still in school are more likely to experience emotional distress, anxiety, or engage in risky behaviors. The implication of this result is that students who feel a strong need to earn money may experience stress, anxiety, or even depression, affecting their well-being. Also, economic pressure may drive students to engage in risky behaviors such as dishonesty, skipping school, or associating with negative influences.

Previous studies corroborated these findings that drive for money increase and endangers students’ psychosocial behavior (Ames et al., 2021; Chassin et al., 2022; Dittmar et al. 2021; Maggs et al., 2023). The authors further agreed that adolescents with a strong focus on acquiring wealth may exhibit more competitive and less cooperative behavior. This competitive drive can strain friendships and reduce opportunities for meaningful social interactions, potentially leading to social isolation.

The second hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between substance abuse and psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescent in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; this means that peer influence and availability of substances do not have a measurable impact on emotional

instability and risky behavior among respondents. This shows that most respondents strongly disagreed with statements indicating substance use, suggesting low levels of drug experimentation. The implication of this result is that, since substance abuse is not a major contributor to psychosocial problems in this study, intervention efforts should prioritize other factors such as economic pressure and mental health support.

Previous studies such as Saxena and Agrawal (2021) and Moksnes et al., (2022) corroborated this findings and affirms that in populations where substance use prevalence is low, its impact on mental health and risky behavior is minimal.

The third hypothesis stated that there is no significant combined influence of substance abuse and drive for money on psychosocial behavior of in-school adolescents in Ilisan-Remo, Ikenne Local Government, Ogun State; Nigeria. Since the overall model is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means that the combination of drive for money and substance abuse significantly influences psychosocial behavior, but drive for money is the dominant factor in this relationship. This result implies that adolescents who feel pressure to earn money while still in school may experience emotional distress, anxiety, or engage in risky behaviors to cope with financial expectations. Since only 20.1% of the variance in psychosocial behavior is explained by these two factors, other influences such as peer pressure, academic stress, or family dynamics may play a more significant role.

Volkow et al., (2022) and Sussman and Lisha (2020) in their studies agrees with the findings of this study. Their study affirms that economic stressor, including financial expectations from families, are key predictors of emotional instability and risky behaviors in adolescents. Similar to this study's findings, Wray-Lake, Crouter, and McHale (2018) emphasized that adolescents under economic pressure may engage in risky behaviors due to anxiety, social comparison, or the need to support their families. Volkow et al., (2022) found that financial concerns among adolescents lead to stress, anxiety, and an increased likelihood of risk-taking behaviors. Their study aligns with this research by confirming that economic stress plays a stronger role in shaping adolescent behavior than substance use does in some populations. The result of Dittmar et al. (2021) demonstrated that financial instability among adolescents leads to a variety of psychosocial challenges, including low self-esteem, academic struggles, and behavioral problems.

Some studies disagreed with the findings of this study, Richins and Dawson (2022) contradicts the current findings by establishing a strong link between adolescent substance use and psychosocial distress. **Their study argue that** substance use is often a coping mechanism for emotional instability and stress, leading to behavioral problems. This contradicts the present study, which found that substance abuse had no significant impact on psychosocial behavior. Chaplin and John (2019) in their study found that substance use contributes to anxiety, depression, and impulsive behaviors in adolescents. The contradiction with the present study may be due to differences in cultural and social environments, where substance abuse may not be as widespread among adolescents in Ilisan-Remo. Also, according to Schulenberg and Maggs (2019), since economic stress was found to significantly impact psychosocial behavior, schools and policymakers should implement financial literacy programs and scholarship opportunities to reduce financial pressure on students. In addition, providing **counseling and career** guidance **can** also help students manage family expectations regarding financial contributions.

Conclusion and Recommended:

As adolescents experience higher drive for money, they may face emotional distress, anxiety, and engage in risky behaviors. While substance abuse did not show a major influence in this particular sample, the drive for money was found to be a dominant factor in shaping psychosocial behavior. The following were recommended:

Provide Career Guidance and Counseling: Adolescents should be offered counseling services and career guidance to manage family expectations and navigate the pressures of academic and financial success. This could help reduce the anxiety and distress associated with financial concerns.

Focus on Social Support Systems: Strengthening social support networks, including peer and family relationships, can provide a buffer against emotional instability. Schools and communities should foster environments that encourage cooperation and reduce competitiveness.

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